



1. The existing definition of agroforestry (AF) in the Rural Development Regulation (“a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land”) should not be changed, but should be clarified to make clear that trees can be inside parcels or on parcel-boundaries.
2. Eight possible agroforestry IACS/LPIS codes are suggested as part of the “EFA Layer” of the IACS/LPIS - related to “non-productive areas” (i.e. GAEC-9).
3. The IACS/LPIS codes for “Landscape Features” include individual trees, lines of trees and groups of trees. Powerful earth observation tools exist to identify these, and all MS should ensure that they are fully mapped in their LPIS system by 2023. They should count towards GAEC-9 and be fully eligible for Basic Payments.
4. The role of Trees outside the Forest should be explicitly recognised in the new Forest Strategy, and “agroforestation” should match existing planned “afforestation” at around 300,000,000 trees per year.
5. MS should implement the Commission’s [Working Paper](#) on direct payments: which says that Member States have the leeway to ensure agricultural area under agroforestry is “fully eligible for Basic Payments when justified based on the local specificities (e.g. density/species/size of the trees and pedo-climatic conditions) and the value added of the presence of trees to ensure sustainable agricultural use of the land”.
6. MS should recognise the potential for agroforestry to contribute to all ten Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC), and mention agroforestry accordingly in their GAEC guidance rules to farmers.
7. Agroforestry within agricultural parcels (called “hectares of agroforestry” in the current CAP) should be included in GAEC-9 areas, irrespective of whether it has been assisted by current or previous Pillar II schemes. This should apply to agroforestry on cropland, grassland and permanent crop areas.
8. Proposals have been made for five Pillar I Agroforestry and Landscape Feature Ecoschemes, which can be undertaken on a sequential annual basis, including planning, establishment and maintenance of existing areas like dehesa, parkland, wood pasture.
9. MS should include Pillar II “Establishment, Regeneration or Renovation of Agroforestry Systems” (aka submeasure 8.2) in their Strategic Plans as the primary way to establish new agroforestry areas and to enhance existing agroforestry like dehesa and wood pasture.
10. MS should include Pillar II “Forest Grazing” as part of the “Forest Protective Infrastructure” (aka sub-measures 8.3 and 8.4) in their Strategic Plans, as a potent means of preventing fires..
11. MS should establish a Pillar II Agroforestry Agri-Environment-Climate Measure (aka submeasure 10.1). This could be included in a Carbon Farming Scheme, which would meet the costs of soil carbon baselining, and subsequent monitoring, reporting and verification.
12. CAP Result Indicator 17 should read “Afforested and Agroforested Land: area in the farm “Reference Area” which is supported for afforestation, reforestation and agroforestation”. This is important since agroforested land remains as agriculture and should be recorded separately from afforestation.
13. Result Indicator 29 - Preserving Landscape Features - is a vital indicator and its removal by the AgFish Council should be reversed.
14. Result Indicators should be reported on annually and should include interventions funded outside the CAP - whose conditions are covered by “EU State Aid to Agriculture and Forestry Guidelines”.
15. All MS give their definition of “forest land” in the LULUCF Regulation. Small patches of tree-cover (e.g. <0.5ha in many countries) are not “forest” but are “Other Wooded Land” or “Other Land With Tree Cover” - using FAO definitions. Net GHG emissions from these areas should legally be reported in national inventories to the UNFCCC within the “grassland” or “cropland” categories. They are best considered as a component of agroforestry.